

Metal Chelate Complexes of the Condensation Products of Biguanides and Salicylaldehyde : Part I. Copper Compounds

S. N. Poddar and A. K. Sarkar

Biguanide and mono-substituted biguanides condense with salicylaldehyde to give compounds of the Schiff base type. The resultant ligands give inner-metallic complexes with transitional metals and different types of complexes are obtained under different conditions of reactions. The present communication deals with copper (II) complexes of such ligands.

Very little is known about the metal-complexation capabilities of the condensation products of amides or amidines with carbonyl compounds. Biguanides, the well-established complexing agents, are essentially amidines and the reaction of the complex chromium(III) and cobalt(III) biguanide bases with mercury(II) chloride in aqueous solution¹ furnishes an evidence of the presence of only one free amino (-NH₂) group in each biguanide molecule in metal-biguanide complex. The presence of a free amino (-NH₂) group in the metal-biguanide complexes has also been demonstrated by the formation of cobalt(III) biguanide silver hydroxide of composition Co(Big-AgOH)₃. aq. by the action of silver nitrate solution on a solution of the cobalt trisbiguanide hydroxide². Further support to this fact has been given by the reaction of copper(II) N'-diethyl biguanide with copper(II)-salicylaldehyde in methanol solution³. Biguanides have been found to condense with salicylaldehyde to produce compounds of the Schiff's base type, the condensation products corresponding to the general formula.

where R=H, CH₃, C₂H₅, C₆H₅;

R'=H, CH₃, C₂H₅.

They are crystalline solids, more or less yellow in colour and are soluble in methanol, ethanol and acetone. Except the one formed by the interaction of phenyl biguanide and salicylaldehyde, these products are decomposed on exposure to air. They are, however, stable when kept in a vacuum desiccator over fused CaCl₂. The compounds are hydrolysed on boiling with water or dilute mineral acids but are somewhat stable in dilute alkalis.

The present communication describes the behaviour of some such compounds obtained from biguanides (both unsubstituted and substituted at one end) and salicylaldehyde towards metal-chelate formation. The preparation and properties of copper(II) complexes of Schiff's bases formed from methyl, ethyl, phenyl, dimethyl and simple biguanides with

1. P. Rây, and S. K. Siddhanta, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **18**, 397.
2. P. Rây and S. K. Siddhanta, *ibid.*, 1941, **18**, 298.
3. P. Rây and N. N. Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1949, **26**, 144.

salicylaldehyde have been given below. The magnetic moment values of the central metal ion of the different complexes have also been measured to study the nature of the complexes and the bond types involved in their formation.

In preparing the copper complexes four different methods as enumerated below were employed :

(A) The metal-biguanide base was first prepared, which was then refluxed with salicylaldehyde in ethanol medium.

(B) The metal-biguanide base was refluxed with the corresponding metal salicylaldehyde complex in ethanolic solution.

(C) The biguanide base and salicylaldehyde in equimolar proportions were refluxed in ethanol for about 2 hr. and the condensation product thus formed (*in situ*) was treated with an ethanolic solution of the metal acetate.

(D) Requisite quantities of the biguanide base, salicylaldehyde and the corresponding metal acetate were refluxed in ethanol.

The methods (A) and (C) gave compounds having a metal-ligand ratio 1 : 2, thus indicating the formation of compounds of general formula CuL_2 where LH is a molecule of the Schiff's base. The method (B), however, gave rise to another type of compound having a ratio of copper to ligand 1 : 1 indicating the formation of binuclear compounds of the type described by Ray and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*). The products obtained by method(D) were of indefinite composition probably due to the formation of mixtures of compounds obtained from methods (A) and (B).

Attempts to prepare salts (such as chloride, nitrate or sulfate) of the metal complexes led, however, to no positive result indicating the absence of basic character of the biguanide part of the molecule of the condensation products. Attempts were also made to prepare similar metallic complexes from ethylenedibiguanide and salicylaldehyde. Analyses of the products obtained revealed that they were heterogeneous mixture of indefinite composition.

The copper(II) complexes of the general formula CuL_2 and Cu_2L_2 as mentioned above may structurally be represented by (I) and (II) respectively.

The copper(II) complexes prepared by methods (A) and (C), and represented by (I) above are all greenish yellow in colour and have magnetic moments corresponding to one unpaired electron. Although from the magnetic data it is not possible to differentiate

between the type of bonds involved in their formation, their colour suggests that the complexes belong to 'outerlevel' or 'associated' type resonating with the ionic ones. In these complexes, the ligands appear to behave as bidentate ones.

The copper (II) complexes prepared by method (B) and represented by (II) above, on the other hand, have magnetic moments ranging from 1.2-1.6 B.M. (at 32°). This sub-normal values of the magnetic moments of the complexes are in conformity with their binuclear structures as shown above with direct metal-metal interaction. In this type of complexes, the ligands appear to exhibit tetradentate functions. It has been observed that though the simple biguanides form Schiff's base with salicylaldehyde, the bis (biguanide)-copper(II) base does not give biguanide-salicylaldehyde copper(II) complex like the substituted biguanide compounds. This apparently anomalous behaviour can be easily explained by taking into account the asymmetric structure of the metal biguanides as suggested by Sen (*private communication*). In the bis (biguanide) copper(II) complex base, the proton has the equal possibility of being available in both the $-NH_2$ groups because of the symmetry considerations and electro-neutrality of the molecule, as shown in figure III. Substitution in one of the two $-NH_2$ groups, however, restricts to some extent the free electron flow, with the consequent development of some polarity in the molecule. A proton under such conditions will seek the more basic site i.e., the substituted $-NH_2$ group, leaving the free one open for attack by the reacting salicylaldehyde.

The formation of the metallic complexes of the condensation products in the cases described above, probably takes place by previous rupture of the metal-nitrogen bonds of the metal-biguanide complexes and subsequent establishment of the same at different sites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper (II) phenyl-biguanide-salicylaldehyde: Preparation by method (A): 4.2 gms of dried copper phenyl biguanide base, prepared according to the method of Ray and Chakraborty⁴ was refluxed on water bath with 2.5 gms of salicylaldehyde in 100 ml of alcohol for about 2 hr. A yellowish green compound precipitated out, which was filtered, washed first with little water and finally with alcohol and dried in air.

The green filtrate from the above gave a further crop of the same product on concentration.

The substance is soluble in alcohol and acetone but insoluble in water. The aqueous suspension is neutral to litmus. It is decomposed by mineral acid but not by dilute alkali solutions. The compound chars on heating and salicylaldehyde is given off.

The substance is paramagnetic ($\mu_B = 1.77$ B.M.) Found: Cu, 9.45%, N, 21.07%, H_2O , 5.28%. Calculated for $Cu(PhBigSal)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, Cu, 9.64%, N, 21.21%, H_2O , 5.46%.

Preparation by method (B) : Copper phenyl biguanide base (0.4 gm) was refluxed with copper salicylaldehyde (0.3 gm) in ethanolic solution for about 2 hr. The resultant dark green solution was filtered to remove any unreacted solid material. The clear filtrate was kept at room temperature for some time when a green product separated out. This was filtered, washed with a little alcohol and dried in air.

The product forms green coloured amorphous powder, practically insoluble in water but sparingly soluble in alcohol. The compound is quite stable at room temperature in the dry state and is decomposed by the action of concentrated mineral acids but not by alkalis. The compound chars on heating and gives off salicylaldehyde.

The substance is paramagnetic ($\mu_B=1.36$ B.M.). Found: Cu, 18.18%, N, 20.13%. Calculated for $\text{Cu}_2(\text{PhBigSal})_2$, Cu, 18.48%, N, 20.35%.

Preparation by method (C) : Phenyl biguanide hydrochloride (2.2 gms) was refluxed with a solution of sodium ethoxide in alcohol (prepared from 0.3 gm of metallic sodium and 100 cc. absolute alcohol) for 2 hr. The precipitated sodium chloride was filtered off. The filtrate was refluxed with salicylaldehyde (1.2 gms) for 2 hr. The resulting yellow refluxate was then mixed with an alcoholic solution of 1.2 gms of copper acetate and the mixture was refluxed for a further period of 1 hr. The resulting green solution was filtered hot. The filtrate on cooling gave a yellowish green compound. This was filtered, washed with a little alcohol and dried in air.

The compound has composition and properties and magnetic moment value identical with those of the product obtained by method (A) above.

Copper(II) ethyl-biguanide-salicylaldehyde. All the above methods were adopted and the compounds obtained by the methods (A) and (C) are identical. They are yellowish green in colour having similar physical and chemical properties to those of the corresponding phenyl biguanide compounds obtained by methods (A) and (C).

The compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_B=1.75$ B.M.). Found: Cu, 11.54%, N, 24.96%, H_2O , 6.13%. Calculated for $\text{Cu}(\text{EtBigSal})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Cu, 11.28%, N, 24.84%, H_2O , 6.37%. The compound obtained by the method (B) is yellowish green in colour having similar physical and chemical properties to the corresponding phenyl biguanide compound obtained by similar method. The compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_B=1.49$ B.M.). Found: Cu, 21.30%, N, 23.40%. Calculated for $\text{Cu}_2(\text{EtBigSal})_2$, Cu, 21.52%, N, 23.69%.

Copper (II) methyl-biguanide-salicylaldehyde : The compound prepared by the methods (A) and (C) is deep green crystalline powder. The bottle green colour of the hot aqueous solution of the compound disappears on addition of dil. HCl but it reappears on making the solution alkaline with dil. NaOH solution. The substance is paramagnetic ($\mu_B=1.72-1.75$ B.M.). Found: Cu, 11.48%, N, 25.3%, H_2O , 6.43%. Calculated for $\text{Cu}(\text{MeBigSal})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Cu, 11.82%, N, 26.04%, H_2O , 6.70%.

The compound prepared by method (B) is green crystalline powder having similar physical and chemical properties to the corresponding phenyl biguanide analogue. The compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_B=1.47$ B.M.). Found: Cu, 22.33%, N, 24.75%. Calculated for $\text{Cu}_2(\text{MeBigSal})_2$, Cu, 22.51%, N, 24.78%.

Copper(II) dimethyl-biguanide-salicylaldehyde: Dark olive green compound was obtained by the methods (A) and (C). The substance is similar both physically and chemically to the corresponding phenyl biguanide compound. The compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_B = 1.98 - 2.00$ B.M.). Found: Cu, 11.35%, N, 24.82%, H₂O, 6.17%. Calculated for Cu(Me₂BigSal)₂ · 2H₂O, Cu, 11.20%, N, 24.67%, H₂O, 6.35%. The method(B) gave a paramagnetic ($\mu_B = 1.35$ B.M.) olive green crystalline powder chemically and physically similar to the corresponding phenyl biguanide compound. Found: Cu, 21.54%, N, 23.82%. Calculated for Cu₂(Me₂BigSal)₂ Cu, 21.37%, N, 23.53%.

Copper(II) biguanide-salicylaldehyde: Copper(II) biguanide base did not react with salicylaldehyde when the mixture was refluxed in ethanol medium.

The method(B), however, produced a green crystalline powder which on analysis was found to correspond with the composition Cu₂(BigSal)₂. The substance is paramagnetic ($\mu_B = 1.21$ B.M.). Found: Cu, 28.55%, N, 25.96%. Calculated for Cu, 23.81%, N, 26.22%. A green crystalline powder was obtained by method(C) which is similar to the copper(II) compound of the substituted biguanide analogues. The compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_B = 1.75$ B.M.). Found: Cu, 12.16%, N, 27.34%, H₂O, 6.76%. Calculated for Cu(BigSal)₂ · 2H₂O Cu, 12.50%, N, 27.72%, H₂O, 7.10%.